

Exchange Behaviour of Coen_3^{3+} on Soil and Peat Humic Acids

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The exchange behaviour of Coen_3^{3+} on soil and peat humic acids (SHA and PHA) shows that the exchange isotherms resemble Langmuir type of curves and the uptake of this complex ion depends on pH. At lower pH, stronger acidic groups, e.g. COOH group predominantly participate in the interactions. The release isotherms obtained by using different electrolytes display the order of reactivity, $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K} < \text{Rb} < \text{Cs} \ll \text{H}$ for the monovalent, $\text{Mg} < \text{Ca} < \text{Sr} < \text{Ba}$ for the bivalent, and $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N} < (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}$ for the organic cations. The exchange isotherms with monovalent cations exhibit that the exchange processes take place in three stages. By using Kielland's equation, thermodynamic equilibrium constants and Gibbs free energy change for exchange reactions involving bivalent cations have been computed. $\log$ of corrected selectivity coefficients or thermodynamic equilibrium constants have been plotted against hydrated ionic radii and the reciprocals of Debye-Hückel parameter a° . The plots suggest that the relative affinities of the counter ions for the exchanger substrates are much better correlated with a° rather than with ionic radii.

WHILE exchange studies on soil organic matter with simple cations¹⁻⁵ including trace elements⁶⁻⁸ have been reported by different researchers little is known about such studies with complex inorganic cations. However, this type of investigations with clay minerals have been done in fundamental details by some workers⁹⁻¹³. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to study the exchange behaviour of Coen_3Cl_3 on soil and peat humic acids to have an understanding on the physicochemical aspects of such exchange processes. Here, the concepts of Pauley¹⁴ and Kielland¹⁵ have been harnessed to interpret the results, the latter in particular, to determine some thermodynamic quantities.

Experimental

Soil humic acid (SHA): The soil collected from the forest (0-15 m depth) of Raja Rammohanpur in the district of Darjeeling (India) moistened overnight with water was shaken with 0.05 M HCl and left over a day for decomposition of carbonates. Finally, washed free of HCl, the soil was treated with 0.3 M NaOH solution. The dark coloured liquid thus obtained was then centrifuged to remove clay substances and humic fractions. The crude humic acid was separated from the centrifugate by acidifying it with dilute HCl to pH 1-2 and freed from the supernatant by centrifugation. The crude humic acid was then dialysed and the dialysed material was subjected to soxhlet extraction with 95% alcohol. The alcohol insoluble fraction of humic acid was dissolved in NaOH and precipitated

at pH 1-2 by addition of HCl. The precipitated humic acid was then repeatedly treated with Amberlite IR-120 resin in the H-form to minimise the ash content.

Peat humic acid (PHA): The peat humus supplied by Fluka-Ag was dissolved in 0.3 M NaOH and centrifuged to remove the alkali insoluble humic fraction. The subsequent operations were exactly similar to those adopted with soil humus.

Elemental analyses show that SHA contains C, 58.4; H, 3.8; N, 3.97; ash content, 1.7%; and PHA, C, 56.91; H, 4.00; N, 0.91; ash content, 0.9%.

SHA and PHA were subjected to various analytical techniques like potentiometry, viscometry, visible and ir spectroscopy, polarography for their characterisation. The b.e.c.'s of these acids were primarily determined by potentiometric titrations with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ and NaOH in presence and in absence of their salts. The exchange behaviours of Coen_3Cl_3 on humic acid systems at different pH were first studied. For this purpose equal portions of the acid suspensions were taken in 25 ml stoppered pyrex bottles. A measured amount of Coen_3Cl_3 of known concentration was added to each bottle. The pH values of these mixtures were varied by adding NaOH and HCl solutions and the volume was made upto 10 ml. The bottles were kept shaking for 1 h and left overnight to equilibrate. The pH values of the mixtures were again determined and they were centrifuged at 20 000 r.p.m.; Coen_3^{3+} contents were polarographically determined using a Radelkis OH-102 polarograph. Next, for the

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exchange isotherm at a particular pH (7.5), increasing amounts of Coen_3Cl_3 were added to different 25 ml pyrex bottles containing equal volumes of acid suspensions. The pH values of these mixtures were raised to 7.5 with NaOH solution and the volume was made upto 10 ml. The subsequent operations were the same as those done in measurements at different pH.

To study the release isotherms, Coen_3 -humic acid complexes were prepared by mixing in each case the acid suspensions with three times its predetermined b.e.c. (with respect to $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of 0.5 M BaCl_2) of Coen_3Cl_3 solution and the pH of the mixture raised to 7.5 with NaOH solution. The mixture was stirred for 2 h. The Coen_3 -humic acid thus formed was centrifuged and the centrifugate dialysed for seven days. The removal of excess Coen_3^{3+} was ensured by polarographic examination. The dialysed complex was then suspended in distilled water and used for exchange studies with different electrolytes. The exchange studies were performed by taking equal portions of the Coen_3 -acid complex in 25 ml pyrex bottle and adding to them the increasing amount of the electrolyte (volume made upto 10 ml) followed by shaking, keeping overnight to equilibrate and centrifuging at 20 000 r.p.m. and Coen_3^{3+} released was determined polarographically. The electrolytes used were of analytical grade and Coen_3Cl_3 was prepared by the method of Jorgensen¹⁶ from ethylenediamine and CoCl_2 by aerial oxidation.

Results and Discussion

The curve (Fig. 1) depicts that the uptake of Coen_3^{3+} by SHA increases with increasing pH; similar curve is obtained with PHA (not shown). It may be ascribed to the increasing dissociation of acidic groups, namely, phenolic OH and COOH present in humic acids normally serving as the active sites for exchange reaction with the rise in pH. In this context, the competition between Coen_3^{3+} and H^+ in solution, particularly at low pH, may also be considered. It is evident from the curves that there is a limiting pH value for each system below which the exchange process practically ceases to function. This is because at these pH values the dissociation of acidic groups in the exchangers is too low and that apart, Coen_3^{3+} cannot vie at all with H^+ at this high concentration of the latter. Further, these curves suggest two stages of interaction one at low (3–4.5) and another at higher pH (4.5–8.0). It may be due to the stronger acidic groups predominantly participating in the exchange process at lower pH while all the acidic groups both weak and strong getting increasingly available for interaction at higher pH. The exchange isotherms of Coen_3 -SHA (Fig. 1) and Coen_3 -PHA (not shown) at pH 7.5 resulting Langmuir type of curves, indicate complete saturation of exchange sites available at this pH after certain concentration of Coen_3^{3+} is added. The b.e.c.'s of the acid systems

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherm of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ -SHA system.

with Coen_3^{3+} obtained from these isotherms are 480 and 500 m. equiv./100 g for SHA and PHA, respectively. These values found by potentiometric titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of 0.5 M BaCl_2 are 472 and 470 m. equiv./100 g of SHA and PHA, respectively.

The exchange isotherms (Fig. 2) with monovalent cations, except H^+ , suggest the exchange processes taking place in three stages. The rate of exchange

Fig. 2. Release of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from Coen_3 -SHA by monovalent cations.

is initially high, then it subsides and then again it rises till it tends to reach a steady value in some cases. It is very likely that the exchanging ions first replace the Coen_3^{3+} from the sites of weak

interaction resulting in high rate of exchange. Subsequently, it attacks the strongly interacted sites so that the rate of exchange decreases; afterwards the exchange process gets easier to some extent because of the increase in the concentration of the exchanging species and finally it heads for a steady state. The H^+ displays an unusually high exchanging ability compared to other cations. This high exchangeability may be explained by assuming H^+ to be bare proton by virtue of which it has got a greater accessibility to the exchange sites. However, despite its high exchange capacity, it could release only 64 and 72% of total Coen_3^{3+} contained in $\text{Coen}_3\text{-SHA}$ and $\text{Coen}_3\text{-PHA}$ complexes, respectively. It indicates that some Coen_3^{3+} ions are so strongly bound with the exchangers that they cannot be replaced under ordinary condition.

The exchange isotherm with bivalent cations and quaternary ammonium ions have been shown in the Figs. 3 and 4. Based on corrected selectivity coefficients and distribution coefficients, the ions

Fig. 3. Release of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from $\text{Coen}_3\text{-SHA}$ by complex by bivalent cations.

Fig. 4. Release of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from $\text{Coen}_3\text{-SHA}$ complex by organic cations.

may be placed in the order, $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K} < \text{Rb} < \text{Cs} \ll \text{H}$ for the monovalent, $\text{Mg} < \text{Ca} < \text{Sr} < \text{Ba}$ for the bivalent, and $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N} < (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$ for the organic cations. For monovalent and bivalent cations, the order is in conformity with the lyotropic series, i.e. it increases with decrease in the hydrated ionic size.

However, for organic cations, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$ shows a greater exchangeability than $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$, although the ionic size of the latter is smaller than that of the former. The higher exchanging efficiency of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$ may be explained by considering the effective charge of this ion being greater than that of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$, because with the latter, CH_3 group attached to N-atom exerts greater hyper conjugative effect.

The selectivity coefficients were computed assuming exchange equilibria as

bars indicating the exchange phase, z, the valency of the exchanging ions. The corrected selectivity is denoted by

$$K_{\text{Coen}_3}^i = \frac{[i^{z+}]^{1/z} a_{\overline{\text{Coen}_3}^{3+}}^{1/3}}{[\overline{\text{Coen}_3}^{3+}]^{1/3} a_{i^{z+}}^{1/z}}$$

where the brackets and a terms represent the concentration and activity of the ionic species under consideration. In as much as no satisfactory data for mean activity coefficients of the ions in the exchanger phase are available, the concentration terms in molalities have been used. To compute the activities, the concentration of the ionic species in liquid phase have been expressed in molalities.

The mean activity coefficients of Coen_3Cl_3 in solution have been calculated by the well known Debye-Hückel formula as used by Kielland¹⁷ considering the ionic radius of Coen_3^{3+} as 3.68 Å as determined by Jenkin and Monk¹⁸ from the limiting equilibrium ionic conductances of Coen_3^{3+} and it is consistent with the crystallographic inter-ionic distance of the complex^{19,20}. The values of mean activity coefficients of the desorbing inorganic ions have been taken from literature^{21,22}. However, for organic cations $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$, no activity corrections have been made. In no case, mutual influence, if any, on the activity coefficients in mixed solution have been taken into consideration. The distribution coefficient is denoted by $\lambda_i = m_i/m_l$ where m_i and m_l are the molal concentrations of the species i in the exchanger and ligand phases, respectively.

The values of the thermodynamic equilibrium constants have been satisfactorily evaluated from the linear plots (Figs. 5 and 6) of the experimental results by using Kielland's equation which is given by

$$\log K_0 = \log K + C[n - 2n\bar{x}_B + (n - m)x_B^2]$$

where, K = thermodynamic equilibrium constant of the general equilibria, $m\overline{A}^{n+} + n\overline{B}^{m+} = m\overline{A}^{n+} + n\overline{B}^{m+}$ bars representing the exchanger phases, K_C = corrected selectivity coefficient, x_B = equivalent ionic fraction of B in the exchanger phase.

TABLE 1—CORRECTED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS, DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen₃-SHA AND Coen₃-PHA COMPLEXES

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolytes M	Distribution coefficient	Corrected selectivity coefficient
Coen ₃ -SHA system			
1 : 1 Electrolyte			
LiCl	0.4 × 10 ⁻¹	21.75	3.25 × 10 ⁻³
	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹	8.73	2.95 × 10 ⁻³
	3.2 × 10 ⁻¹	4.81	2.95 × 10 ⁻³
NaCl	0.41 × 10 ⁻¹	18.57	3.94 × 10 ⁻³
	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹	11.45	3.86 × 10 ⁻³
	3.3 × 10 ⁻¹	4.57	3.23 × 10 ⁻³
KCl	0.4 × 10 ⁻¹	17.2	4.56 × 10 ⁻³
	1.6 × 10 ⁻¹	7.79	3.39 × 10 ⁻³
	4.0 × 10 ⁻¹	3.0	4.51 × 10 ⁻³
PbCl	0.51 × 10 ⁻¹	13.25	5.04 × 10 ⁻³
	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹	6.0	3.81 × 10 ⁻³
	3.1 × 10 ⁻¹	3.26	5.26 × 10 ⁻³
CaCl	0.6 × 10 ⁻¹	10.59	5.76 × 10 ⁻³
	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹	7.79	4.43 × 10 ⁻³
	3.7 × 10 ⁻¹	2.50	6.14 × 10 ⁻³
HCl	0.1 × 10 ⁻¹	1.36	3.58 × 10 ⁻¹
	0.4 × 10 ⁻¹	0.68	2.68 × 10 ⁻¹
1 : 2 Electrolyte			
MgCl ₂	0.9 × 10 ⁻³	5.13	0.154
	2.7 × 10 ⁻³	3.04	0.135
	3.4 × 10 ⁻³	2.64	0.131
CaCl ₂	0.8 × 10 ⁻³	5.13	0.163
	2.3 × 10 ⁻³	2.50	0.172
	3.0 × 10 ⁻³	1.88	0.167
SrCl ₂	0.69 × 10 ⁻³	3.81	0.220
	2.06 × 10 ⁻³	2.08	0.202
	3.4 × 10 ⁻³	1.55	0.191
BaCl ₂	0.8 × 10 ⁻³	3.41	0.216
	2.3 × 10 ⁻³	1.91	0.206
	3.2 × 10 ⁻³	1.48	0.208
Quaternary ammonium salts			
(OH ₄) ₄ NCl	0.42 × 10 ⁻¹	20.96	2.17 × 10 ⁻³
	1.7 × 10 ⁻¹	7.70	1.93 × 10 ⁻³
	3.3 × 10 ⁻¹	4.75	1.72 × 10 ⁻³
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NCl	0.38 × 10 ⁻¹	21.0	2.40 × 10 ⁻³
	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹	8.10	1.96 × 10 ⁻³
	3.0 × 10 ⁻¹	4.9	1.87 × 10 ⁻³
Coen ₃ -PHA system			
1 : 1 Electrolyte			
LiCl	0.38 × 10 ⁻¹	14.52	3.27 × 10 ⁻³
	1.9 × 10 ⁻¹	3.79	3.52 × 10 ⁻³
	3.5 × 10 ⁻¹	1.83	4.38 × 10 ⁻³
NaCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	13.86	3.35 × 10 ⁻³
	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹	3.46	3.91 × 10 ⁻³
	3.7 × 10 ⁻¹	1.72	4.68 × 10 ⁻³
KCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	13.05	4.36 × 10 ⁻³
	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹	3.16	4.50 × 10 ⁻³
	3.6 × 10 ⁻¹	1.49	5.64 × 10 ⁻³
RbCl	0.50 × 10 ⁻¹	10.54	4.22 × 10 ⁻³
	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹	2.90	5.08 × 10 ⁻³
	3.6 × 10 ⁻¹	1.31	6.47 × 10 ⁻³
CaCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	9.40	5.6 × 10 ⁻³
	1.6 × 10 ⁻¹	2.67	6.82 × 10 ⁻³
	3.2 × 10 ⁻¹	1.23	7.88 × 10 ⁻³
HCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	0.33	7.76 × 10 ⁻¹

(Table 1 contd.)

1 : 2 Electrolyte			
MgCl ₂	0.90 × 10 ⁻³	4.68	0.122
	2.7 × 10 ⁻³	1.72	0.151
	3.6 × 10 ⁻³	1.40	0.151
CaCl ₂	0.94 × 10 ⁻³	4.20	0.178
	2.8 × 10 ⁻³	1.08	0.203
	3.7 × 10 ⁻³	0.92	0.187
SrCl ₂	1.0 × 10 ⁻³	2.28	0.198
	1.7 × 10 ⁻³	1.60	0.195
	2.8 × 10 ⁻³	1.00	0.199
BaCl ₂	0.8 × 10 ⁻³	2.06	0.234
	1.6 × 10 ⁻³	1.48	0.210
	3.3 × 10 ⁻³	0.89	0.236
Quaternary ammonium salts			
(OH ₄) ₄ NCl	0.8 × 10 ⁻¹	6.82	2.65 × 10 ⁻³
	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹	4.20	1.87 × 10 ⁻³
	2.8 × 10 ⁻¹	2.90	2.01 × 10 ⁻³
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NCl	0.90 × 10 ⁻¹	5.20	3.22 × 10 ⁻³
	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹	4.10	2.49 × 10 ⁻³
	2.1 × 10 ⁻¹	2.80	2.68 × 10 ⁻³

Fig 5. Plot of Kielland's equation in the exchange of [Coen₃]³⁺ from Coen₃-SHA complex by bivalent cations.

Standard Gibbs free energy has been calculated from the relation $\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln K$. The results are incorporated in Table 2. No attempt has, however, been made to use Kielland's equation for determination of thermodynamic equilibrium constants for exchange reactions involving monovalent cations because in such cases the postulates of Kielland's equation do not seem to hold good in view of the

Fig. 6. Plot of Kielland's equation in the exchange of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{2+}$ from Coen_3 -PHA complex by bivalent cations.

continuous dissolution of the exchanger phase in water as the exchange reaction goes on.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES EVALUATED FROM KIELLAND'S EQUATION AT 25° FROM THE EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen_3 -SHA AND Coen_3 -PHA COMPLEXES

Exchange system	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant $\times 10$		ΔG° cal mol ⁻¹	
	Coen_3 -SHA	Coen_3 -PHA	Coen_3 -SHA	Coen_3 -PHA
$K_{\text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Mg}}$	0.87	1.74	1 454.7	1 043.0
$K_{\text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Ca}}$	1.41	1.86	1 166.5	1 001.8
$K_{\text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Sr}}$	1.62	1.95	1 084.1	974.4
$K_{\text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Ba}}$	1.96	2.32	974.4	871.4

The plots of $\log K$ for the divalent and $\log K_0$ at arbitrarily chosen concentration (0.40 and 0.32 M for Coen_3 -SHA and Coen_3 -PHA, respectively) for the monovalent cations against hydrated ionic radii and the reciprocal of the Debye-Hückel parameter a° are given in Figs. 7 and 8. It is observed that while there is a sharp break in each of the $\log K_0$ vs hydrated ionic radii²³ curves, $\log K_0$ vs $1/a^\circ$ curves are fairly linear. Similar is the case with the bivalent cations. The $\log K$ vs hydrated ionic radii²⁴ plots are not linear, $\log K$ vs $1/a^\circ$ plots demonstrate perfect linearity for all the four cations under consideration. It amply suggests that K or K_0

Fig. 7. Correlation between selectivity coefficient K_0 and (a) hydrated ionic radii and (b) Debye-Hückel parameter a° in the exchange of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{2+}$ from Coen_3 -SHA at 0.4 M electrolyte concentration by monovalent cations.

Fig. 8. Correlation between thermodynamic equilibrium constant and (i) hydrated ionic radii and (ii) Debye-Hückel parameter a° in the exchange of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{2+}$ from Coen_3 -SHA complex.

values correlate much better with a° rather than with the hydrated ionic radii. Similar observations have also been made by Das Kanungo *et al.*^{9,13} with the desorption of Coen_3^{2+} from Coen_3 -clay minerals. Incidentally, the $\log K$ or $\log K_0$ vs $1/a^\circ$ is based on Pauley's model which suggests that electrostatic attraction between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups is the significant factor to reckon with in the ion-exchange process.

Display of curves in connection with Coen_3 -PHA system has generally been avoided because they are found to yield similar type of curves as shown by Coen_3 -SHA system.

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